

Inhibitors Of Administration of Quality Secondary Education: A Case Study of a Local Government Area in Cross River State, Nigeria

Garieth Omorobi Omorobi^{1*}, Idorenyin Clement Eton², Ojobe Ojobe Egbai³

¹Department of Educational Management, University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria.

² Institute of Education, University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria

* Corresponding Author

Email: omobi4christ@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study was carried out to assess principals' perception of inhibitors of administration of quality secondary education among public secondary schools in Biase Local Government Area in Cross River State, Nigeria. The survey research design was adopted to carry out the study. All the thirty-eight 38 principals and Vice principals of public secondary schools constituted the population and sample of the study using the census approach. An instrument titled: Principals' Perception of the Inhibitors of Administration of Quality Secondary Education Questionnaire (PPIAQSEQ) was developed by the researcher. The face validity of the instrument was established by three experts in Educational Management and Measurement and Evaluation all in the University of Calabar, using Cronbach's alpha reliability, the instrument obtained an alpha coefficient of .81. Data was collected and analyzed through simple percentages. The findings of the study revealed that averagely over 70 % of the respondents either agree or strongly agree that quality of teachers, teachers' salary, promotion pattern, availability of teachers, teacher welfare, industrial action, lack of instructional materials, delayed salary, teacher attrition, lack of libraries, lack of monthly impress, laboratories, textbooks, and lack of desk strongly inhibited administration of quality secondary education in Biase LGA of Cross River State, Nigeria. It was concluded that addressing the problem of funding will address if not completely a reasonable portion of the quality problems faced by the secondary education subsector. Consequently, it was recommended Government should ensure adequate budgetary allocation to education in line with UNESCO's benchmark of 26% of total annual budgetary allocation to education for developing nations.

Keywords: Administration, education, inhibitors, principal, quality, secondary.

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Introduction

Secondary education anywhere in the world is purposefully designed and dedicated to the training and development of the youths (Etim, 2007 & World Bank, 2006). It is primarily saddled with the responsibility of equipping the youths of a nation with relevant knowledge and skills needed for survival within the society. According to the World Bank (2006), it is globally acknowledged as the cornerstone of educational systems in the 21st century. Therefore, the

quality of secondary education remains essential in providing a bright future for the youths as well as the nation as a whole.

However, education and secondary education, in particular, has suffered a high level of neglect in most societies especially in developing nations like Nigeria (Ekundayo, 2019). This is because of low political will and lip service rendered to this level of education by the government. Consequently, Lawal (2018) observed that successive Nigerian governments in the last four decades have paid lip service towards revamping the education sector. Regrettably, it has been decried that, the sector remains bedevilled by low budgetary allocation, poor incentives for teachers and dilapidated infrastructure (Mbon, Omorobi, Owan & Ekpenyong, 2019). Figures of annual budgetary allocation have continued to dwindle between 9.94%, 7.74%, 6.10%, 7.38% and 7.03% in 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018 and 2019 respectively (Central bank of Nigeria, 2019). This however contravenes the UNESCO benchmark of 26% annual budget allocation to education for developing countries. Therefore, the quality of secondary education in the country continue to fall simultaneously with falling budgetary vote. The government seems to talk more about the crises facing education rather than act on resolving them.

According to Akufo-Ado (2017), discussions on education should not only focus on providing access to education but also on the quality of education provided. Quality according to Babalola (2007) is most often defined as fitness to purpose in relation to the user and customer needs. It also means that the product conforms to standards, specifications or requirements. In the words of Bamisaiye (1983) quality may be defined as the sum composite of the properties inherent in a material or product. Secondary education is said to be of high quality when its graduates possess the requisite knowledge, skills and values required for contributing to the development of the society as well as smooth integration into the society. Quality secondary education enables youths to express more fully their potential capacities. It also involves the conformity of education inputs and processes to set standards namely facilities, funds, teachers, teaching and learning process among others; that enable the production of sound school leavers.

The quality of secondary education largely depends on several factors such as availability of quality teachers, instructional, facilities, adequate funding, among other things (Mbon et al, 2019). According to Longe (1999) quality education encompasses the learning environment (process) and students' outcomes (grandparents). Similarly, Gbenu (2012) identified indicators of quality education to include the quantity and quality of inputs to education, relevant curriculum, appropriate teaching methods and the quality of teaching aids, adequate and suitable infrastructural facilities, student-teacher ratios, students-classroom ratios, well-organized mid-day meals, planning, administration and efficiency of inspection and supervision, nursery and kindergarten schools, special education for the handicapped; conditions of school attendance which include distance which children walk to school and the distribution of hours among the different subjects in the syllabus, availability of suitable textbooks, well equipped library and resource centers for teachers and students, the proportion of the trained men and women in the teaching force, good system of record-keeping, continuous

assessment of learning activities and experiences, reliability of examinations in use, the quality of learning that is achieved, parents' positive or negative attitudes to education, cultural and religious views in the local community, and the living levels of children's families, their health and nutrition. The grandaunts of a quality secondary school system should be able to prove their worth by their level of performance in the competitive labour market among other challenges that will confront them in society.

The quality of education is more often than not operationalized, quantified and measured through students' academic performance in their terminal external examination such as the West African Senior School Certificate (WASSCE). Therefore, students' academic performance remains a strong and most reliable index of school quality. Lawal (2018) pointed out that in both 2017 and 2018's January/February external GCE, only 26.01 per cent and 17.13 per cent candidates passed with five credits including Mathematics and English respectively; while the remaining over 70 per cent candidates failed. Similarly, mass failure was recorded in the 2017 WAEC exams where only 34,664 out of 131,485 had five credits including English and Mathematics. Also, the percentage of candidates that passed WASSCE, for external candidates, in 2015 and 2016 was 28.58 per cent and 38.50 per cent, respectively. This indicates a general fall in the quality of education and if the trend continues it will jeopardize the future of today's youths and the generation after them.

Regrettably, it is becoming more difficult for modern school administrators to lead the desired change in schools. This is because, no matter how effective and efficient principals are, they cannot achieve quality education without the necessary resources in place (Eton & Omorobi, 2020). This includes a team of qualified and motivated teachers, adequate instructional resources and funds. Hence, the absence and or inadequacy of these very essential human and material resources could pose a serious challenge to the administration of quality secondary education in Biase. It has been observed that these constraints faced by principals in a bid to ensure the administration of quality secondary education has resulted in the perceived lack of knowledge and skills needed by many school leavers to actively participate in the society as well as record intolerably poor grades in external examinations. The quality of school leavers from many secondary schools has been oftentimes criticized for lacking the requisite skills and knowledge expected of them. Gbenu (2012) x-rayed the situation in Nigerian secondary schools to include dilapidated Schools/structures, collapsed infrastructure, the population is increasing, teacher supply and quality are declining, poor methods of ensuring quality within the education industry. These factors have in no small measure inhibited the quality of teaching and learning process in the school thereby resulting in poor quality of school leavers.

A major setback to enhancing school quality in Nigeria is poor funding. This is often reflected in the system through low and fluctuating annual budgetary allocation to education that is acutely below UNESCO's 26% benchmark for developing nations. Lawal (2018) reported that even after promising a declaration of a state of emergency on education, in the 2018 appropriation bill presented to the National Assembly, President Buhari allocated only 7.04 per cent of the N8.6 trillion 2018 budget to education. The total amount allocated to the sector is N605.8 billion with N435.1 billion for recurrent expenditure, N61.73 billion for capital

expenditure and N109.06 billion for the Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC). Therefore, stakeholders have argued that no amount of 'declaration of a 'state of emergency' in the sector can change the reality.

Teaching refers to the act of facilitating students learning experiences often carried out by a teacher. The quality of the teaching and learning process and by extension education highly depends on the quality and quantity of teachers. Lack of teachers and ineffective teachers could influence the quality of education at any given point in time. The national policy on education, the Federal Government of Nigeria (2013) maintains that no level of education can grow above the level of its teachers. Therefore, the teacher is very crucial in ensuring the Quality of education. Hence, Nagoba and Mantri (2015) describe teachers as the main ingredients in giving quality education.

Apart from the teacher instructional resources are also very essential materials responsible for enhancing quality education. Instructional resources encompass classrooms, desks, a public address system, textbooks, projectors, computers, whiteboards that facilitate the teaching and learning process in the classroom. According to Lewis (2018) Instructional Materials, also known as Teaching/Learning Materials are any collection of materials including animate and inanimate objects and human and non-human resources that a teacher may use in teaching and learning situations to help achieve desired learning objectives. Instructional materials may aid a student in concretizing a learning experience to make learning more exciting, interesting and interactive. It encompasses all the materials and physical means an instructor might use to implement instruction and facilitate students' achievement of instructional objectives. Instructional materials can be classified on their types, which include prints, visuals, audiovisuals Textbooks, pamphlets, handouts, study guides, manuals, Cassettes, microphone Charts, real objects, photographs, transparencies, slides, tapes, films, filmstrips, television, video, multimedia, The shortage or lack of adequate instructional resources of the right type could hinder a teacher from achieving the best in terms of effective delivery of classroom instruction as well as negatively affects the quality of secondary education. Babayomi (2009) found that private schools performed better than public schools because of the availability and adequacy of teaching and learning materials. Mwiria (2008) also supports that students' performance is affected by the quality and quantity of teaching and learning materials.

Another critical resource that enhances the quality of secondary education is funded, in facts finance remains a very essential resource in any organization and the school in particular. This is true because funds are needed for the remuneration of teachers as well as the procurement of all instructional resources. Hence, when it is inadequate or in short supply, it hinders the entire functioning of the school system. Chiefly, finance remains the primary reason for recurring industrial actions in our school that constantly truncate academic activities in school. When teachers are not paid, or irregular payments of salaries, arrears and other benefits reduce their commitment, morale, and increase attrition tendencies.

Nwafor, Uchendu and Akani (2015) in their study on the need for adequate funding in the administration of secondary education found a positive relationship between quality of school output and quality of funding. It was also found in their study that inadequate funding of secondary school results in infrastructural decay, high cost of education, low level of staff commitment. Olagboye (2004) listed some of the challenges of quality secondary education to include the following: Supervisors lack training in supervisory competencies because some supervisors were promoted based on seniority and length of service but not appropriate training and qualification; inadequate provision of infrastructural facilities, teaching aids and instructional materials in schools, Poor remuneration of teachers and poor conditions of service which reduces their commitment to teaching, the poor status accorded to teachers which dampen their morale and job satisfaction, presence of a large number of untrained and unqualified teachers in the school system, teachers' poor attitude to work and lack of interest in teaching. Similarly, Babalola (2007) on his own listed the following as some of the challenges especially as it relates to inspection which is a tool for sustaining quality education, use of unqualified and untrained personnel in the inspectorate services which result in poor quality control, shortage of manpower in the inspectorate; lack of adequate statistical compilation in the school system, inadequate funds and resources for inspection; lack of training for would-be school inspectors, inadequate facilities in the inspectorate etc. hence, this study investigated the students' perception of inhibitors quality secondary education among public secondary schools in Biase LGA.

Statement of the problem

Recently, the public, government, parents and the press have constantly mounted pressure on school principals about the steady decline in standards of education particularly in public secondary schools in Cross River State, Biase inclusive. Chief among their reservations about the falling standards of education has been the poor academic performance of students especially in external examinations like WASCE and NECO. Hence, these stakeholders have blamed principals for their failure to ensure effective administration of quality secondary education that can ensure high students performance. To address this challenge government has only built classroom blocks for each public secondary school in the Area. But it seems this is not enough or adequate as the problem persist. This could be due to some systemic quality inhibitors other than those known by the public. Consequently, the study took an inward approach by using the administrators to assess perceived inhibitors of administration of quality secondary in Biase LGA.

Purpose of the study

This was designed to assess the inhibitors of the administration of quality secondary education.

Research question

What are the perceived inhibitors to the administration of quality secondary education?

Methods

This study was carried out to assess principals' perception of the inhibitors of administration of quality secondary education among public secondary schools in Biase Local Government Area in Cross River State Nigeria. The survey research design was adopted to carry out the study, the design was the most appropriate for the study because the phenomenon is an ongoing activity in schools. Therefore, the researcher only collected, analyzed data and described relative incidences. All the thirty-eight 38 principals and Vice principals of public secondary schools constituted the population and sample of the study using the census approach. There were considered appropriate because they are directly involved in the management of secondary schools. An instrument titled: Principals' Perception of the Inhibitors of Administration of Quality Secondary Education Questionnaire (PPIAQSEQ). The face validity of the instrument was established by three experts in Educational Management and Measurement and Evaluation all in the University of Calabar, the reliability of the instrument was established by administering the instrument to fifteen (15) public school principals in Calabar, who were not part of the study using the Cronbach's alpha reliability, the instrument obtained an alpha of coefficient of .81. Data was collected by the researcher by visiting each school and administering it to the principals and vice-principals. After data collection, simple percentages were used for the analyses.

Results

Research question 1

What are the perceived inhibitors to the administration of quality secondary education? The results on table one showed that all the items inhibited the quality of education as follows: for items 1, quality of teachers about (79% or 30 respondents); 2 (71% or 27 respondents); 3(87% or 33 respondents); 4(76% or 29 respondents); 5(74% or 28 respondents); 7 (74% or 28 respondents); 8(71% or 27 respondents); 9 (58% or 22 respondents);10 (84% or 32 respondents); 11(84% or 32 respondents); 12 (68% or 26 respondents); 13 (76% or 29 respondents); 14 (66% or 25 respondents); 15 (76% 29 respondents) respectively either agree or strongly agree that quality of teachers, teachers salary, promotion pattern, availability of teachers, teacher welfare, industrial action, lack of instructional materials, delayed salary, teacher attrition, lack of libraries, lack of monthly impress, laboratories, textbooks, and lack of desk strongly inhibited the quality of secondary education in Biase LGA of Cross River State, Nigeria. However, items 6 & 16 that is teacher transfer and administrative space did not inhibit the administration of quality secondary education.

Table 1: Mean ratings of principals' perceived inhibitors to the administration of quality secondary education

S/N	Items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD%	Remark
1.	Quality of Teachers	25(65.78)	5 (13.15)	6(15.78)	2(5.26)	S.A
2.	Teacher salary	19(50)	8(21.1)	8(21.1)	3(7.89)	SA
3.	Teachers' promotion	15(39.47)	18(47.36)	5(13.15)	—	SA
4.	No. of teachers available	20(52.63)	9(23.68)	6(15.78)	3(7.89)	SA
5.	Welfare packages	12(31.5)	16(42.10)	5(13.15)	5(13.15)	SA
6.	Teachers transfer	6(15.78)	4(10.52)	20(52.63)	8(21.1)	SD
7.	Industrial actions	22(57.89)	6(15.78)	2(5.26)	8(21.1)	SA
8.	Avail. of instructional Materials	18(47.36)	9(23.68)	10(26.31)	1(2.63)	SA
9.	Delay in teachers' salary	16(42.10)	6(15.78)	8(21.1)	8(21.1)	SA
10.	Teacher attrition	20(52.63)	12(31.5)	4(10.52)	2(5.26)	SA
11.	Lack of libraries	18(47.36)	14(36.84)	4(10.52)	2(5.26)	SA
12.	Lack of impress	17(44.73)	9(23.68)	11(28.94)	1(2.63)	SA
13.	Lack of laboratories	19(50)	10(26.31)	6(15.78)	4(10.52)	SA
14.	Inadequate textbooks	17(44.73)	8(21.1)	10(26.31)	8(21.1)	SA
15.	Availability of Desks	18(47.36)	11(28.94)	9(23.68)	—	SA
16.	Administrative space	8(21.1)	4(10.52)	16(42.10)	10(26.31)	SD

* (SA= Strongly agree, A= Agree, D= Disagree, SD Strongly disagree)

Discussion of findings

The findings of the study revealed that averagely over 70 % of the respondents either agree or strongly agree that quality of teachers, teachers' salary, promotion pattern, availability of teachers, teacher welfare, industrial action, lack of instructional materials, delayed salary, teacher attrition, lack of libraries, lack of monthly impress, laboratories, textbooks, and lack of desk strongly inhibited the quality of secondary education in Biase LGA of Cross River State, Nigeria. However, items 6 & 16 that is teacher transfer and administrative space did not inhibit the administration of quality secondary education.

The findings of this study appear to showcase the effect of the lip service paid to the secondary education subsector over the years. For instance, teachers are the backbone of any educational system yet, the quality of teachers sent to most schools in Cross River State are not qualified to be called teachers. Recently, several misgivings were registered on both electronic, social and print media over the politicization of teacher recruitment conducted by the State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB) sometime in 2018, where those who were qualified and indeed performed credibly in the oral and written interview and were assured by the chairman of getting the job were rigged out by mediocre who did not in any way participate in the recruitment process possibly due to their connections with politicians or their capacity to pay their way. Therefore, principals are no magicians to do the extraordinary with absolutely unqualified teachers. Hence, the quality of education will continue to be at par or remain at

equilibrium with the quality of its teacher as rightly affirmed by FGN (2013) no educational system can outgrow the level of its teacher.

Secondly, it was also revealed that level teachers' salary, promotion pattern, availability of teachers, teacher welfare, industrial action, lack of instructional materials, delayed salary, teacher attrition, lack of libraries, lack of monthly impress, laboratories, textbooks, and lack of desk strongly inhibited the quality of secondary education in Biase. All these indicators that inhibited the administration of quality secondary education are directly or indirectly connected to the poor quality of funding to education.

Teachers, though committed with the responsibility of producing lawyers, doctors, accountants and engineers are paid the lowest salary in Nigeria hence, the status and image of the teaching profession are relegated to the dust. Therefore, the teaching profession cannot attract the best young brains due to the laughable conditions teachers are subjected to in Nigerian society. They are noted for indebtedness, living in slumps, hardly own a car, let alone building a personal descent house of their own. Hence, they are not motivated to put in their best in the job and constantly scouting out for greener pastures. Consequently, until our nation recognizes the place of education and accord its rightful place in society by avoiding paying lip service to education the nation will know no true development. The findings of the study are in tandem with the findings of Nwafor, Uchendu and Akani (2015) in their study on the need for adequate funding in the administration of secondary education that, a positive relationship exists between the quality of school output and quality of funding. It was also found in their study that inadequate funding of secondary school results in infrastructural decay, high cost of education, and low level of staff commitment.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the main inhibitors of administration of quality secondary education fundamentally include the quality of its teachers, poor teachers' salary, inadequate promotion pattern, availability of teachers, poor teacher welfare, incessant industrial actions, lack of instructional materials, delayed salary, teacher attrition, lack of libraries, lack of monthly impress, laboratories, textbooks, and lack of desk. However, all of these indices are linked to poor funding of education. Hence, it was concluded that addressing the problem of funding will address if not completely a reasonable portion of the quality problems faced by the secondary education subsector.

Recommendations

It was therefore recommended as follows:

1. Government must ensure adequate budgetary allocation to education in line with UNESCO's benchmark of 26% of total annual budgetary allocation.
2. Teachers' salaries must be improved if the quality of education must be enhanced.

3. Instructional facilities such as must be upgraded in secondary schools Across Biase LGA to meet up modern standards of the learning environment as well as support the instructional demands of the 21st century.

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